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ABSTRACT

The new 767 medium range wide body transport will be the first Boeing commercial aircraft to commit advanced composite materials to initial production. Composite materials, mainly fiberglass in an epoxy matrix, have been used in Boeing military and commercial aircraft in ever increasing amounts for the last twenty plus years, but only recently has the State-of-the-Art of Advanced Composites, graphite and graphite/Kevlar hybrids in an epoxy matrix, progressed to the level required for the commitment to full scale production. This commitment to production on the 767 is the result of a multi-year, multi-million dollar development program to assure technology readiness, producibility, and the product reliability required to meet the stringent performance and safety standards of a modern commercial transport.

As part of the development program, representative advanced composite components were selected, designed, fabricated, and tested. The representative components, which were limited to secondary structure, included parts such as elevators, rudders, ailerons and spoilers. All these parts are presently committed to production as graphite structure on the 767. The original predictions were conservative in that they did not foresee the development and applications of a hybrid composite of graphite and Kevlar which have been effectively applied to the lesser loaded areas of the airplane structure. As the designers became more familiar with composite design techniques the components became increasingly cost and weight effective. New applications were continually being proposed and the number of committed applications grew, including a significant amount of systems and interiors applications.

Although the 767 is primarily an aluminum airplane the committing of significant amounts of composite materials to the initial production is a significant milestone to the time when a future commercial transport will be primarily an all composite airplane.

COMPOSITES IN THE BOEING 767

Committing advanced composites to structural applications at the initial design phase of the 767 program is a tremendous forward step for aircraft structures design technology. This commitment by The Boeing Company was no simple decision. It was the result of many years and millions of dollars in development and testing of advanced composite materials and design concepts.

Aluminum, which has been and will continue to be for the near future the primary aircraft structural material, has been in development for more than a half century. Some very costly and tragic errors were made in the development of both aluminum alloys and aluminum design techniques. Today's social and economic environment demand that similar "fatal flaws" be identified and eliminated in the development of advanced composites.

Structural design in aluminum has been optimized and service proven to be extremely efficient and reliable, but it has also been optimized to the point that significant improvements in terms of lighter weight are not available. To achieve greater weight efficiency the structures designer has little choice but to turn to new materials.

The Boeing Company has been working with composite materials, mainly fiberglass in an epoxy matrix, for well over twenty years. The 727, designed in the early sixties, was the first Boeing commercial transport with a significant amount of fiberglass composite components. These applications were mainly fairings, interior components, and other lightly loaded applications but it was the beginning of the evolutionary progress of composite materials in aircraft structure.

Serious design studies for the structural application of advanced composites started at Boeing in the mid sixties. At that time boron filament was considered to be the most promising material. As studies, component fabrication, and testing continued it became increasingly clear from an economic and practical standpoint that graphite or carbon filament should be the prime material.

Graphite material, was in the early seventies, developed to the point that production design and fabrication techniques were ready to be developed and airline service experience acquired. One of the most significant programs to acquire this data was the Boeing/NASA 737 spoiler program.

FIGURE 1

The 737 graphite composite spoiler flight service evaluation program consisted of the fabrication and flight service experience of 111 graphite-epoxy spoilers on 737 aircraft and the ground based environmental exposure of hundreds of graphite-epoxy material specimens. Spoilers were installed on 28 aircraft representing seven major airlines operating throughout the world. As of April 30, 1979 a total of 1,188,367 spoiler flight hours and 1,786,837 spoiler landings have been accumulated by this fleet.

Based on visual, ultrasonic, and destructive testing there has been no significant evidence of moisture migration into the aluminum honeycomb core and no core corrosion. Tests of removed spoilers and of ground based exposure specimens indicate only modest changes in graphite composite strength.

The encouraging experience of the 737 graphite spoiler program was being observed very closely by the 7X7 (predecessor of the 767) program personnel. Other representative development components fabricated with graphite material also demonstrated a significant weight saving but the risks of committing advanced composites to the initial production of the 767 were still formidable. The most significant advanced composite concerns at that time were:

- No material or process specifications
- No qualified material or sources
- No material design allowables
- Few experienced design and staff engineering personnel
- No advanced composites design manual
- Limited fabrication experience
- No production fabrication experience
- Few experienced fabrication personnel
- Limited inspection procedures
- Few qualified inspection personnel
- No established repair procedures
- Limited service experience
- Limited cost/weight evaluations

With only a year and a half left to go before anticipated formal go-ahead on the production 767 program the list of advanced composite concerns continued to grow and seemed insurmountable.

7X7 program management recognized the economic importance to the airlines of the large potential weight saving offered by advanced composites and launched the 7X7 Advanced Composite Development Program (7X7 ACDP). The primary objective of this development program was to obtain sufficient advanced composite experience on which to base a combined engineering and operations recommendation to 7X7 program management for committing advanced composites to the initial production of the 767.

From the very start, the 7X7 ACDP was given the highest priority. Significant resources were committed both in money and personnel to the development program. A detail plan was developed to answer each concern and work was started immediately in the selection of advanced composite candidate components. The initial selection is shown in Fig 2. The program was divided into multiple phases and work was started simultaneously on these phases. Material screening was initiated, test specimen and sub-component designs were started and full scale components were selected and the designs started.

Figure 2— Advanced Composite Candidate Components

At the beginning of 7X7 ACDP it was estimated the use of graphite composite would produce a weight saving in the production airplane of just under 450 kilograms (1000 pounds). Much was learned in the early phases of the development program. Unfortunately most of this new knowledge added additional concerns which had not been fully recognized at the beginning of the program. One example of this new knowledge was the demonstration that the galvanic corrosion potential between graphite and aluminum was shown to be much more severe than originally suspected. This new concern turned out to be the primary reason why the floor beams, because of their intimate contact with aluminum primary fuselage structure, were later dropped as an advanced composite candidate. Another potential problem uncovered was the loss of strength due to small uninspectable impact damage to the interlaminar matrix.

By midpoint of the development program the estimated production airplane weight saving had dropped to less than half of the original estimate. The cost estimates had climbed to a point that most of the applications were questionable from a cost/weight standpoint. Also at this time it became evident that the pultrusion process, a shape fabrication method for advanced composites, which drastically reduced layup manhours, was not going to be production ready by the 767 production go-ahead and had to be dropped. Since pultrusions, the main cost reduction process, were not available, the designers were forced to go back to the drawing boards to either increase the weight savings or use other methods to reduce cost to obtain the required cost/weight effectiveness.

Figure 3– Pultrusion System

All was not bleak however, many of the over 1000 test specimens and 100 subcomponents had been fabricated and tested. The data from testing these components definitely verified that the weight savings were available.

The cost effectiveness question was still paramount. By this time the fabrication experience was filtering back to the designers. Experience had shown that the use of graphite cloth was more layup time efficient than the use of graphite tape, standardization of ply orientation to 0° , 90° , and $+45^{\circ}$ would also reduce layup manhours. Designing for the use of male tooling instead of female tools could also reduce layup manhours. These and many other similar items when incorporated into the designs significantly reduced fabrication costs.

During this re-examination the designers also looked very closely at the lightly loaded components, such as fairings, which were designed more by minimum gage than by strength or stiffness. Three existing programs had been identified and examined quite closely by the 7X7 advanced composite development designers as having potential application for these lightly loaded areas. These programs were:

1. A NASA/Lockheed program for the substitution of Kevlar fiber for fiberglass fiber in composite panels was presently being flight service evaluated by Lockheed on three L1011 aircraft. The Kevlar fiber has similar properties to fiberglass fiber but is 25% lighter. The results to date for this program had been highly successful.

Figure 4— Kevlar Service Evaluation

2. A Boeing YC-14 program of combining graphite and fiberglass together in a co-cured hybrid composite to take advantage of the best properties of each material. The high strength and stiffness of the graphite and the low cost of the fiberglass.

Figure 5— Lay-Up of YC-14 Main Landing Gear Door

3. A Boeing/Rohr program to develop a Kevlar/graphite hybrid lower cowl panel for the 727 side engines. This hybrid combined the high strength and stiffness of graphite and the low density and moderate cost of Kevlar.

FIGURE 6

Because of the advancements made by these three programs, the 7X7 ACDP designers started to investigate the applicability of hybrid composite applications for the 7X7. A number of components were identified as potential applications and an additional hybrid phase was added to the 7X7 ACDP. The first task was to narrow the program to a single hybrid composite. The potential weight savings of the Kevlar/graphite hybrid was higher than the fiberglass/graphite combination so this was selected as the material combination for the 767.

About this same time production plans for the 767 were being developed and a concerning fact became evident. Those components which were the primary candidates for advanced composites were for the most part the same components which lent themselves to be sub-contracted. An additional concern was that the 767 program was to be an international effort and the two main sub-contractors, or participants as they are defined on the 767 program since they also provide engineering support, would be Aeritalia of Italy and CTDC of Japan.

Figure 7 – 767 Composite Components Produced by Aeritalia

Figure 8 – 767 Composite Components Produced by CTDC (Fuji Heavy Industries)

The 7X7 advanced composite development program was again expanded to include both Aeritalia and CTDC. Engineers and Operations personnel from both participants came to Seattle and joined the Boeing development team. They worked side by side with their Boeing counterpart in nearly every phase of the development program.

Figure 9—

Start of Lay-Up of Full Scale Aileron at Boeing-Seattle With Aeritalia Personnel Observing

Figure 10—

Lay-Up of ECS Door at Boeing Seattle With Fuji Heavy Industries Personnel Observing

The final phase of the participant technology transfer program was the fabrication of identical components at the participants facilities. When a sub-component or full scale component was completed at Boeing, the tools were airfreighted to the participants facilities in Italy or in Japan and the components were fabricated by the participants personnel with Boeing personnel witnessing. These components were then tested and the results compared to the Boeing fabricated component test results to ensure consistent quality.

By the time of the critical milestone of the 7X7 ACDP, the commitment recommendation to management, an advanced composites concerns list still existed but answers for each item were considered achievable.

- Material and Process Specifications had been published
- Multiple sources and materials had been qualified
- Preliminary design allowables had been published
- A cadre of experienced design and staff engineering personnel were available
- An Advanced Composite Design Manual had been published
- Fabrication experience was increased
- Still no production fabrication experience
- Experienced fabrication personnel available (limited)
- Inspection procedures developed
- Qualified inspection personnel available (limited)
- Repair procedure development program established
- Limited service experience
- Encouraging cost/weight evaluations
- Galvanic corrosion concern became workable
- Design allowables to account for uninspectable impact damage

With the addition of the hybrid composite applications the estimated production airplane weight saving was back to its original level of 450 kilograms (1000 pounds) and the production costs had been reduced significantly.

The 7X7 Advanced Composite Development Program recommendation to upper management shortly before the full go-ahead of the 767 production program was:

Engineering - Commit advanced composites to production in selected applications

Operations - Continued development was required, but no fatal flaws identified. Operations could support the commitment of advanced composites to the production 767 airplane

Management accepted this recommendation and at the 767 production go-ahead date, advanced composites were an approved material for secondary structural applications but this acceptance was by no means the end to advanced composite development.

Although the formal 7X7 development program was completed, the data from this and other composites programs has been continually incorporated into the Advanced Composite Design Handbook and issued to the 767 project design engineers. The 7X7 ACDP personnel joined the production program in key positions to train others in their experience of all aspects of composites design and fabrication.

Additional composite applications continued to be identified in the structural areas. The systems and interiors designers also recognized the potential for weight savings of advanced composites and incorporated them in a number of applications. The applications of composites to these areas imposed special conditions, besides weight and cost effectiveness, on the design engineer. These special conditions include severe corrosive environments, flammability requirements, and demanding aesthetic requirements. All these requirements were proven to be best satisfied with a variety of composite materials.

Figure 11– 767 Composite Structural Applications

Figure 12– 767 Composite Interiors and Systems Applications

The present weight saving contributed by advanced composites to the 767 are as shown in Figure 13. This weight saving which is over twice the original 7X7 estimate is actually conservative. A number of applications have not been considered in anything but composite material so the difference in weight with other materials is not included.

Graphite	Spoilers – Inboard and Outboard Outboard Ailerons Inboard Aileron Panels Rudder Elevators	426 Kilograms (938 Pounds)
Hybrid	Wing Fixed T.E. Panels Cowl Components Wing-to-Body Fairing Main Landing Gear Doors Nose Landing Gear Doors Stabilizer Fixed T.E. Panels Stabilizer Seal Plates Lower L.E. Access Panels	246 Kilograms (542 Pounds)
Kevlar	Stabilizer Tips T.E. Flap Linkage Fairings Strut Fairings ECS Ducts Cargo Liner Stowage Bins Emergency Escape System Components Lavatories Closets Partitions Inboard Flap Debris Protection	249 Kilograms (548 Pounds)
		Total 921 Kilograms (2028 Pounds)

Figure 13– Advanced Composite Weight Saving Summary

Operations continued the fabrication development of advanced composites. They had already determined they could produce aircraft quality components but the main concern now was could they continue to achieve quality and quantity on a demanding production schedule. A Production Readiness Program was initiated utilizing many of the same personnel from the 7X7 Advanced Composite Development Program. Selected components were fabricated in multiple quantities to a representative production schedule. This program, which was well ahead of the actual production requirements, identified and solved a number of potential production problems ahead of the time they would become critical to the production program.

Figure 14– Graphite Rudder Cover Panel of the Production Readiness Program

Figure 15– Hybrid Main landing Gear Door of the Production Readiness Program

Economic conditions will force future commercial transports to continue to become increasingly more efficient and sophisticated. Since present composites technology can be compared in development phase to aluminum technology of the 1930s, the areas of further research and development are almost limitless. Future generations of commercial aircraft will have significantly greater amounts of composite material and without any doubt, composites in primary structures. This continued evolution can only occur through the teamwork of further research by the composite scientist and ingenuity of application by the staff engineer and production designer.